

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PREVENTING SOCIAL ISOLATION AMONG THE ELDERLY THROUGH ACTIVITIES CONDUCTED IN DAY CENTRES

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Abstract

This paper investigates the phenomenon of social isolation among the elderly, analysing its causes and implications, as well as the prevention strategies implemented at the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly. In a context marked by an ageing population and the weakening of informal support networks, social intervention becomes essential in promoting the social inclusion of the elderly. The research is based on a theoretical approach centred on the concepts of social isolation, loneliness, exclusion, day care centres, and social work, developed by using a qualitative investigation, conducted through semi-structured interviews applied to the centres beneficiaries and to the multidisciplinary team members that coordinate its activities. The results show that the regular participation of elderly in cultural, educational, and recreational activities helps reduce feelings of loneliness, strengthens social ties, and improves overall psychological wellbeing. The paper thus highlights the essential role of the services provided in day care centres and the importance of community-based intervention in supporting an active and dignified life for the elderly.

Keywords: social isolation, elderly, social inclusion, day care centres, community intervention, multidisciplinary team, social connection, social worker.

Research Relevance

Social isolation of the elderly is one of the most serious social issues in contemporary society, particularly in the context of a rapidly ageing population and transformations in the structure of family and community relationships. In Romania, this phenomenon is exacerbated by the migration of young people, by declining birth rates, and by the weakening of informal support networks. According to recent data, approximately 30% of elderly individuals live in solitude- a percentage that continues to rise as life expectancy increases. [9]

Social isolation is not limited to the absence of social contact; it also involves the exclusion of the elderly from support networks, community life, and access to essential resources such as social services, healthcare and educational or recreational activities. This state of isolation profoundly affects the quality of life, physical and mental health, as well as the elderly's self-perception. Current research confirms that social isolation is a major risk factor for depression, anxiety, and dementia, as well as for the worsening of chronic illnesses such as cardiovascular conditions and mobility disorders. [3, 8]

In this context, day care centres for the elderly become essential in preventing and fighting social isolation. These institutions provide a safe and welcoming environment where they can engage in activities tailored to their needs, ranging from educational and recreational programmes to psychological counselling and support in maintaining an active lifestyle. Studies conducted by Ionescu and Popescu [4] highlight the beneficial role of these centres in reducing feelings of lone-

liness and enhancing the sense of belonging to the community. Regular participation in group activities, the exchange of experiences, and the professional support provided contribute to maintaining the elderly's cognitive and emotional wellbeing.

Caused and effects of social isolation. Solutions

The causes of social isolation among the elderly are complex and varied, and may result from a combination of individual, social, and economic factors. Among the most common causes the following were highlighted: the loss of a life partner, retirement, relocation to a more remote area, and financial or mobility difficulties. [2] These significant changes in an elderly's lives can drastically reduce their social networks and interactions with family and friends.

Social isolation can have devastating effects on the elderly's physical and mental health, and recent research highlights the considerable impact this phenomenon can have on their quality of life. Studies suggest that social isolation is a leading cause of depression in the elderly, with a direct impact on their cognitive health. An essential aspect of understanding social isolation is the strong connection between it and the lack of access to essential services such as medical care, educational activities, or recreational events.

One solution could be the day care centres for the elderly, which offer services designed to support an active and independent life, with a focus on creating an environment that facilitates their participation in social and cultural life. These centres, according to the specialized literature, are intended to provide opportunities

for social, educational, and recreational interaction, helping seniors overcome challenges related to health, mobility, or the lack of a supportive family network. [1] Thus, the activities carried out in such centres are not limited to physical care but also include an important psychosocial component.

Research shows that involvement in educational activities helps maintain an active mind and can prevent premature cognitive decline. [10] Therefore, through lifelong learning activities, seniors are encouraged to actively participate in social life, acquire new skills, and interact with other members of the community.

Recreational activities, essential in fighting the negative effects of social isolation, are particularly important for maintaining the seniors' physical and mental well-being. They help reduce stress, stimulate active social behaviour, and improve self-esteem.

Within the centre, the elderly are encouraged to participate in activities that involve teamwork, group discussions, and mutual support, offering them the opportunity to share their experiences, listen to others, and form meaningful social bonds. These social activities not only help develop close relationships but also facilitate involvement in various community projects and initiatives, thus enhancing the sense of belonging and social cohesion. Increasing participation in community life and seniors' involvement in the activities organized by day care centres also has a direct impact on their integration into the community. Collaboration between day care centres for the elderly and other institutions is essential to ensure comprehensive and integrated support for seniors. According to Johnson and Smith [5], the involvement of local authorities in supporting older adults plays a significant role in increasing access to social services and combating their social isolation.

Collaboration with educational and lifelong learning institutions is crucial for promoting lifelong learning among older adults.

Partnerships with social work agencies also play an essential role in supporting the elderly, providing direct services such as help with managing income, legal counselling, and support in cases of abuse or neglect. The cooperation between day care centres and these agencies contributes to creating a comprehensive support framework for older people, helping them access all the rights and services they are entitled to.

Within this collaboration, day care centres can facilitate access to social services, while social work agencies can offer additional resources and direct support to the elderly, contributing to their integration into society and reducing their isolation. [6]

Analysis and interpretation of the results

The qualitative research implied the use of the semi-structured interview method, allowing a flexible and in-depth exploration of elderly's perceptions regarding the impact of the activities carried out at the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly, as well as the role of the multidisciplinary team coordinating the centre's activities.

The aim of the research was to evaluate the impact of the activities organised by the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly on the social and emotional well-

being of its beneficiaries, as well as the role of these activities in preventing social isolation and the forms of support provided by the multidisciplinary team.

The general objective of the research is to investigate how the activities carried out within the Day Centre contribute to reducing social isolation and improving the elderly's quality of life. [7]

Interview Guide for Elderly Beneficiaries of the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly

The specific objectives target key aspects of the elderly's experience, who attend the Day Care Centre, contributing to a detailed understanding of the role this type of social service plays in preventing social isolation. Each objective addresses a different dimension of the phenomenon under investigation:

- identifying the elderly's perception of social isolation prior to participating in the Day Care Centre's activities;

- identifying the reasons why older adults choose to take part in the centre's activities and how these influence their sense of social belonging, aiming to understand both personal and social motivations (such as the need for interaction, emotional support, or the desire to stay active), as well as the impact of participating on feelings of integration, support, and recognition within the community.

The interview guide was applied to 20 elderly, aged between 65 and 88, and is structured around two thematic units, each containing five supporting questions.

Thematic unit 1: Elderly's perception of social isolation prior to joining the day care centre

Analysing the responses provided by the participants reveals that, prior to joining the Day Care Centre, the majority experienced an acute state of social isolation – "*days marked by oppressive silence*", "*I was living in a form of self-isolation*", "*I had no friends or close family to visit or even call me*", "*a feeling of abandonment and deep sadness*".

The lack of regular social interaction, the loss of loved ones, and the absence of a structured environment for socialising led to negative effects on both their mental and even physical health. Participants reported feelings of loneliness, sadness, and uselessness – "*I feel useless and hopeless*", "*negative thoughts would not leave me*" – and their health was adversely affected – "*episodes of high blood pressure and frequent anxiety*", "*restlessness, chest pain, and difficulty breathing*", "*my sleep was broken and restless*".

The triggering factors for enrolling at the Centre were either recommendations from other beneficiaries – "*conversations I had with a neighbour in my building who was already attending the centre*", – or information provided by social workers or through the community network – "*a visit from the neighbourhood social worker, who gave me an informational brochure about the services offered by the Day Care Centre*".

The responses from the beneficiaries of the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly paint a profound picture of life lived in social isolation prior to joining this service. Most participants described an existence marked by silence, routine, the absence of meaningful human interaction, and a severe lack of

emotional support. Communication was minimal or non-existent, and family relationships, where they existed, did not provide the necessary emotional support.

In conclusion, the first thematic unit highlights the extent and depth of the effects of social isolation among the elderly, as well as the urgent need for structured social services to address these emotional and relational deficiencies. Integration into a setting such as that offered by the Day Care Centre has proven to be, for many, not just a practical solution, but a genuine return to life.

Thematic unit 2: The impact of the Day Care Centre's activities on the social and emotional life of the elderly

The analysis of the responses in this thematic unit indicates a significant positive impact of the activities carried out within the Day Care Centre on the beneficiaries. Regular participation in social, cultural, and recreational activities contributes to restoring emotional balance, increasing self-confidence, and strengthening the sense of belonging. The relationships formed between beneficiaries are based on mutual support and empathy, and the general atmosphere encourages free expression and the restoration of well-being. The preferred activities are those that involve interaction and creativity, which are perceived as key factors in combating loneliness.

The beneficiaries interviewed spoke candidly about how these activities have helped to restore their self-esteem, significantly reduce their feelings of social isolation, and rekindle their personal motivation for life – *“social activities, especially the conversation club and creative workshops”, “I can express myself freely”, “I escape from everyday worries”, “at the creative workshops, I rediscovered that I still have good ideas”*.

For many of them, everyday interactions at the centre turned into genuine friendships, sources of support and belonging, but also emotional anchors in a context where loneliness had become overwhelming – *“I can share stories from my life with other people who listen to me with interest and understanding, which makes me feel valued”, “during those moments, I forget about pain, loneliness, and deprivation”, “I wake up in the morning with a real purpose and motivation, knowing that interesting activities and people with whom I can exchange a few words await me”*. This social network formed within the centre led to an improvement in daily mood, a resumption of contact with the local community, and a rediscovery of personal meaning, even in old age – *“I feel that I am part of a process that enriches me spiritually and connects me with others”, “every meeting has a positive impact on me: it energizes me, cheers me up, and makes me feel important in the lives of others”, “the atmosphere at the Day Care Centre is like that of an extended family”*.

In conclusion, the Day Care Centre is not perceived as a mere social institution, but as a place of personal renewal, where the elderly can rebuild their social and emotional lives in a climate of respect, safety, and encouragement.

Interview guide applied to the multidisciplinary team of the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly

The specific objectives focus on aspects of the multidisciplinary team's experience in working with elderly people at the day centre, namely:

- identifying professionals' perceptions of social isolation among the elderly;
- analysing the impact of the activities carried out at the centre with the beneficiaries, from the perspective of the multidisciplinary team.

The interview guide for the multidisciplinary team was structured into two thematic units, each with five supporting questions. Six members of the multidisciplinary team were interviewed: the social worker, the psychologist, the medical assistant, the community assistant, the centre coordinator, and a physical therapist.

Thematic unit 1: Professional perception of social isolation among the elderly

From the specialists' perspective, the elderly's social isolation is a profound phenomenon with emotional, physical, and relational impacts. It manifests itself through *“visible resignation and lack of involvement, lack of family ties, withdrawal from community life, and feelings of uselessness are among the most common aspects”* (social worker), *“emotional emptiness, fear of rejection, affective disorders, especially depression and generalized anxiety. I constantly observe a lack of hope, fear of rejection, and a tendency to avoid forming new relationships. Withdrawal from activities, avoidance of eye contact, and difficulty expressing one's needs. Isolation becomes a defence mechanism against a world perceived as indifferent or even hostile”* (psychologist), *“many elderly people who come to us show clear physical signs: fluctuating blood pressure, lack of appetite, sleep disorders, weight loss, or somatization of anxiety states”* (medical assistant), *“A major factor that I consider decisive in the emergence of social isolation is the deep rift between generations,” “older people do not feel seen or heard”* (centre coordinator), all based on emotional loss, generational distance, and lack of a support framework.

Integration into the activities of the Day Care Centre brings about significant changes – *“Beneficiaries who were initially withdrawn now smile more often, become active and involved”, “They now come up with their own ideas for activities or suggest topics for discussion. Their interpersonal relationships are improving significantly, and their willingness to collaborate is increasing”* (social worker), *“the transformation is visible on an emotional and cognitive level”*. *“They regain their self-esteem and motivation”, “they return to behaviours they had abandoned years ago — they read, take care of their physical appearance, ask questions, tell stories, and take an interest in others”* (psychologist).

The role of the multidisciplinary team is vital, through empathy, collaboration, and personalized intervention, in supporting social reconnection and emotional balance — *“We detect the subtle signs of social isolation. This is done through initial and periodic assessments, informal discussions with beneficiaries, but also by observing everyday behaviours, participation*

in activities, degree of interaction, tone of voice, willingness to talk. Once we identify a possible risk, we bring the case to the attention of the multidisciplinary team. During regular meetings, each case is discussed and reviewed, and interventions are determined based on individual needs. Close collaboration with colleagues from other specializations helps us build a complete picture and intervene coherently and effectively" (social worker), *"Together we establish an intervention plan that may include individual counseling, support in group activities, or simple actions to reconnect emotionally. Each case is treated as a whole, and collaboration is essential to meet the complex needs of beneficiaries"* (psychologist), *"My role is essential in connecting the Centre with the beneficiaries' external environment. Home visits and discussions with neighbours or family members give us a real picture of the living context. I constantly communicate with the team about what I observe in the field, and we adjust our interventions based on this information"* (community assistant).

The specialists' responses highlight that social isolation among the elderly is a common reality, with profound effects on their emotional, mental, and physical well-being. It manifests itself through withdrawal, apathy, lack of initiative, and loss of meaning in life.

The factors that cause this isolation are diverse: personal losses, health problems, poverty, lack of family support, and generational rifts. The effects are visible in depression, somatic disorders, lack of motivation, and neglect of self-care.

Integration into the activities of the Day Care Centre generates clear positive changes: beneficiaries become more active, more involved, and regain self-confidence. The multidisciplinary team plays an essential role through early risk identification, constant assessments, and coordinated interventions. Collaboration between specialists is the key to effective and personalized support.

Thematic unit 2: The impact of the centre's activities on the elderly

The specialists at the Day Care Centre note that carefully structured activities facilitate social integration and give seniors a sense of belonging. The social worker notes the gradual opening up of the beneficiaries, who become more involved and confident. *"Group activities, such as themed clubs (literary, culinary, conversation) or social evenings, provide the ideal context for beneficiaries to interact in a natural and empathetic way"*. The psychologist notes clear signs of emotional balance, genuine smiles, a desire to express themselves, and initiative. *"Personal development workshops and emotional support groups play an essential role in combating social anxiety and feelings of uselessness commonly found among the elderly"*. The physical therapist confirms this progress through the seniors' increased motivation to take care of their physical condition: *"The beneficiaries participate in exercises on their own initiative, request additional routines, or remember the movements and do them at home. Their inner state has improved, and their bodies 'speak' of regaining control and hope"*. Through the efforts of the multidisciplinary

team, the personalization of interventions stimulates reconnection, self-esteem, active involvement, and supports dignified and meaningful aging.

The analysis of the multidisciplinary team's responses clearly shows that the activities carried out at the Day Care Centre have a profound and positive impact on the social, emotional, and physical well-being of the elderly. Regular participation in creative workshops, games, intergenerational activities, and themed meetings not only reduces feelings of isolation but also encourages active involvement, regains self-confidence, and forms genuine bonds between beneficiaries. The transformations observed, from increased emotional and physical tone to the emergence of individual initiatives, are the direct result of a personalized intervention, carefully tailored to the needs of each beneficiary. In this sense, the effective and flexible collaboration of the multidisciplinary team plays an essential role, allowing for the early identification of vulnerabilities and the construction of a coherent and empathetic support framework. The proposed activities thus become not just ways of passing the time, but genuine tools for social reactivation, emotional healing, and restoring personal meaning in old age.

Conclusions

The research conclusively showed that the social isolation of the elderly is a profound social problem with multiple emotional, relational, psychological, and physiological dimensions. The results obtained from the application of the interview guidelines to both beneficiaries and members of the multidisciplinary team at the Caransebeş Day Care Centre for the Elderly allow us to draw clear and well-founded conclusions that validate the importance of activities focused on social inclusion and psychosocial support in fighting this phenomenon.

Firstly, it is clear that integration into an active, organised and empathetic social environment has a transformative effect on the elderly. The beneficiaries' responses reveal that the simple act of breaking out of physical isolation (leaving the house, participating in group activities) triggers a series of positive emotional processes, among which the following stand out: regaining personal dignity, rebuilding support networks, building friendships, and revaluing oneself. The elderly described the centre not as a simple activity space, but as a new existential landmark, a supportive community where they feel seen, heard, and accepted.

Secondly, the centre's multidisciplinary team contributes decisively to shaping a complex therapeutic and relational framework. The professionals' responses clearly show that the intervention is not limited to specific actions, but is a continuous process of observation, adaptation, communication, and support for each beneficiary, depending on their particularities. The collaboration between the psychologist, social worker, medical assistant, community assistant, physical therapist, and coordinator not only ensures the coherence of the intervention, but also creates a network of psychosocial security in which the elderly can reinvent themselves.

A fundamental aspect noted in both guides is the role of collective activities: creative workshops, gymnastics, discussion groups, community events, and intergenerational projects prove to be not only means of socialization but also therapeutic tools with dual value, fighting against psychological stress and reducing the feeling of social uselessness. These activities promote reconnection with meaning, offering older people the opportunity to get involved, express their opinions, and contribute to something greater than themselves.

The research also highlighted a notable consistency between the beneficiaries' perceptions and the specialists' observations: both categories validate the positive impact of the centre on the emotional, functional, and social well-being of the elderly. This congruence between lived experience and external observation reinforces the conclusion that day care centre intervention is not only beneficial but essential for maintaining psychosocial balance in old age.

Day centres for the elderly are emerging as one of the most effective forms of social intervention because they act simultaneously on several levels: they fight against loneliness, promote socialization, provide primary care, emotional support, and, above all, restore meaning and belonging.

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